

Profit shifting of multinational corporations in the European Union and worldwide^{*}

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Summary

1. We reveal the distributional consequences of profit shifting of multinationals.
2. We estimate that firms shifted over \$850 billion in profits in 2017, primarily to countries with effective tax rates below 10%.
3. Countries with lower incomes lose a larger share of their total tax revenue.
4. As methodological contributions, we exploit the new country-by-country reporting data and we propose a logarithmic function to capture the extremely non-linear relationship between profits and tax rates
5. We highlight effective tax rates' importance for profit shifting and tax reforms.

1. Introduction

Corporate tax avoidance contributes to the view of globalisation as inequitable. Publicised case studies, such as those based on the Panama and Paradise Papers, have detailed how little some large multinationals pay in corporate income tax as a result of their **profit shifting to low-tax jurisdictions or tax havens**.

We still lack reliable estimates on the origin and destination of profit shifting for many countries worldwide, which is necessary to understand the potential **effects of international tax reforms**, despite recent growth in research interest in tax havens generally (Zucman, 2013, Bilicka, 2019, Alstadsæter et al., 2019, Cobham & Janský, 2020) and profit shifting in particular (Cobham & Janský, 2018, Janský & Palanský, 2019, Clausing, 2020, Álvarez-Martínez et al., 2021, Garcia-Bernardo et al., 2022, Tørsløv et al., 2023).

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In this study, we exploit a new dataset and develop a novel methodology to address the question of the **distributional consequences of profit shifting of multinationals worldwide**. Specifically, we answer the following four research questions: (i) What is the scale of profit shifting? (ii) Which tax havens are the largest? (iii) Which multinationals are the most aggressive in profit shifting? (iv) Which countries lose the most relative to their total tax revenues?

These intrinsically linked research questions lack definitive answers due to both data-related and methodological challenges. Profit shifting as a form of **tax avoidance** cannot be directly observed and it is not clear how economists should estimate it. However, the data utilised as well as the choice of function to model the relationship between tax rates and profits have crucial implications for answers to our research questions.

We address these challenges by using a new country-by-country reporting dataset with vastly improved country coverage and by modelling the extreme non-linearity of that relationship — **two methodological contributions** that we now outline before proceeding to our main findings.

2. Methods

Our first methodological contribution is to pioneer the use of **country-by-country reporting** by multinationals, alongside several other concurrent studies. These unique data were first made available in 2020 thanks to a new regulation, which emerged from the Base Erosion and Profit Shifting project by OECD, that requires all large multinationals to report profits and taxes in every country, including tax havens and low-income countries. For example, the US

country-by-country reporting data include 25 African countries, while the frequently used US Bureau of Economic Analysis data only include three.

We provide our own **estimates of profit shifting for a total of 214 countries** using data from 38 headquarter countries, including the major economies of the United States, China and India. While country-by-country reporting data include the most reliable country-level information on tax payments and profits of multinationals worldwide, it aggregates small countries into categories (e.g. “Other Africa”), and might be prone to double-counting of profits due to a lack of clarity in reporting of intercompany dividends and so-called stateless entities. We address the double-counting of profits by developing a method for estimating missing data, disaggregating categories into individual countries, and eliminating double-counting of dividends.

Our second methodological contribution is that we propose to model **the extremely non-linear relationship** between profit location and multinationals’ tax rates using a logarithmic function (Figure 1). We build on literature that confirmed the existence of profit shifting, pioneered by, e.g., Hines & Rice (1994). The headline specification of that approach assumes a linear semi-elasticity, which Dowd et al. (2017) show to underestimate profit shifting to low-tax jurisdictions. They instead introduce a quadratic semi-elasticity, which does constitute an improvement.

However, we show that not even the quadratic model is capable of capturing the empirically observed extreme non-linearity in the data: 85% of profit shifted takes place towards countries with tax rates below 10%. In this paper, we therefore introduce a **logarithmic**

model to fully capture the extreme non-linearity of the semi-elasticity of profits to tax rates.

Although estimates of the global scale of profit shifting are similar for linear, quadratic and logarithmic functions as well as a simpler misalignment model measuring the difference between locations of profits and economic activity, they differ substantially at the country level: the logarithmic function and the misalignment model point to **profits being shifted relatively more to countries with zero or very low effective tax rates**. This naturally has implications for the estimated distributional consequences of profit shifting to tax havens.

3. Results

We apply the logarithmic model to the country-by-country reporting data to establish the scale and distribution of profit shifting in many countries worldwide, revealing **four main findings** that answer the four research questions outlined above.

First, **multinationals shifted over \$850 billion in profits to tax havens in 2017**, which in turn implies \$200–300 billion in revenue losses for other countries. Our total estimates of profit shifting are broadly comparable to existing estimates such as Tørsløv et al. (2023), who estimate profit shifting to be \$616 billion in 2015 and \$969 billion in 2019. By combining our modelling approach with the extreme non-linearity and exceptionally high coverage of our dataset (214 countries), we arrive at semi-elasticity estimates that are consistent with higher shares of profits in tax havens.

Second, we proceed to estimating which tax havens are the largest. The large majority of shifted profits are shifted to a small group of

countries with extremely low effective tax rates, defined as the ratio of accrued taxes over profits. We find that **the Cayman Islands, Luxembourg, Singapore**, Canada, the Netherlands, Switzerland, Hong Kong, Bermuda, Puerto Rico and Ireland are the largest destination of profits (Figure 2). In contrast with the consistent estimates across models of the overall scale, the largest tax havens – as well as the countries affected by them – differ substantially between models. The United Kingdom is seen as a source of profits in the misalignment model, while a recipient of profits (given its low tax rate) in other models.

The misalignment and logarithmic model agree that **the vast majority of profits in small tax havens (e.g., the Cayman Islands or Luxembourg) are shifted there**, while the quadratic and linear models are not able to capture the extent of profit shifting. Moreover, high-income countries capture most of the tax revenue gains due to being destinations of profit shifting.

Third, among headquarter countries reporting on over 20 jurisdictions, multinationals headquartered in the United States, Brazil and Singapore are the **most aggressive in terms of profit shifting**. In contrast, we find no evidence of profit shifting towards tax havens by multinationals headquartered in South Africa and Malaysia.

While a great deal of previous research has been carried out on US-headquartered multinationals due to data availability, our results highlight that they are not necessarily representative of all multinationals and that there are important differences across countries. Consequently, policymakers might negotiate international agreements differently if they know how aggressive their own multinationals are in comparison with other

countries' multinationals with respect to profit shifting.

Fourth, we contribute to the ongoing discussion of which countries lose more tax revenue due to profit shifting. Country-by-country reporting data has much higher country coverage of 214 countries and includes many lower-income countries for the first time. We find that it is precisely these **lower-income countries that tend to lose more tax revenue due to profit shifting relative to their total tax revenue** (Figure 3), directly contravening one of the goals of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, namely to: “Strengthen domestic resource mobilisation, including through international support to lower-income countries, to improve domestic capacity for tax and other revenue collection”.

In absolute terms, the **United States** is estimated to suffer the most from profit shifting while other high-income countries such as **Germany and France** are estimated to lose up to half of their profit base in this manner.

4. Conclusions

Overall, **our study's enhanced methodology and data provide a possible resolution** to the inconsistency between so-called micro and macro estimates of profit shifting found in existing literature. Specifically, the relatively low (micro) estimates of tax semi-elasticity in earlier studies (Beer et al., 2020, Heckemeyer & Overesch, 2017) could not explain the (macro) estimates of the high shares of profits reported by multinationals in tax havens (Dharmapala, 2019, Zucman, 2015).

We show that one explanation for the apparent inconsistency is the manner in which the relationship between profits and

tax rates has been modelled using mostly linear and, far less frequently, quadratic functions. When we instead use a logarithmic function to allow for the relationship's extreme non-linearity, we arrive at **high estimates of tax semi-elasticity at low levels of effective tax rates** and, consequently, a very high share of profits in a number of tax havens with low effective tax rates. While the country-by-country reporting data may need to be provided at firm level or for several years to facilitate even more nuanced findings, such as on the incidence or industry heterogeneity of profit shifting worldwide, our improved methodology and dataset do help reconcile the micro and macro estimates.

Our findings provide **two key policy-related insights**. First, the extremely nonlinear relationship between the location of profits and tax rates has implications for both research and policy. In research, we show that accurately accounting for this relationship affects the estimated scale and distribution of profit shifting. In policy, this modelling choice can significantly influence the assessment of international tax reform, as may be the case with **the global minimum tax rate agreement reached in 2021, so-called Pillar Two**. While this assessment assumes that profit shifting incentives decrease in linear fashion as the minimum effective tax rate increases, we show in this paper that this linearity assumption is unlikely to hold. Our findings indicate the importance of the specific value of the minimum effective tax rate, which is 15% in the case of Pillar Two.

Our second key insight is based on our finding that lower-income countries tend to lose more tax revenue relative to total tax revenue due to profit shifting. This could nudge their governments into using confidential tax return data for more detailed analyses. In

policy, our results indicate that the current international tax system may be hindering the achievement of one of the goals of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development: to **strengthen domestic resource mobilisation**. This supports the arguments of lower-income countries that they should be represented on an equal footing at reform discussions and that such reforms should be geared towards creating a level playing field in the corporate taxation of multinationals.

What is DemoTrans ?

DemoTrans is an impact-driven research project that will provide theoretically and empirically robust recommendations on how to reinvigorate democratic governance by improving the accountability, transparency, effectiveness and trustworthiness of rule-of-law based institutions and policies.

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Figures

Figure 1. Profit per employee as a function of the ETR using the OECD data. [Source](#): Garcia-Bernardo & Janský (2024).

Figure 2. Profits shifted in and out of countries. [Source](#): Garcia-Bernardo & Janský (2024).

Figure 3. Tax revenue loss as a percentage of total tax revenue. [Source:](#) Garcia-Bernardo & Janský (2024).

Further Information:

Garcia-Bernardo & Janský (2024): Garcia-Bernardo, J., & Janský, P. (2024). Profit shifting of multinational corporations worldwide. *World Development*, 177, 106527. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2023.106527>.

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